

FBI CRIME DATA PREDICTION USING MACHINE LEARNING WITH DATA ANALYSIS

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Abstract:

Crime is one of the biggest and dominating problem in our society and its forestallment is an important task. diurnal there are huge figures of crimes committed constantly. This bear keeping track of all the crimes and maintaining a database for same which may be used for future reference. The current problem faced are maintaining of proper dataset of crime and assaying this data to help in prognosticating and working crimes in future. The ideal of this design is to dissect dataset which correspond of multitudinous crimes and prognosticating the type of crime which may be in future depending upon colorful conditions. The crime data is uprooted from the sanctioned gate of police. It consists of crime information like position description, type of crime, date, time, latitude, longitude. Before training of the model data preprocessing will be done following this point selection and scaling will be done so that delicacy gain will be high. The K- Nearest Neighbor(KNN) bracket and colorful other algorithms will be tested for crime vaticination and one with better delicacy will be used for training. Visualization of dataset will be done in terms of graphical representation of numerous cases for illustration at which time the felonious rates are high or at which month the felonious conditioning are high. The soul purpose of this design is to give a idea of how machine literacy can be used by the law enforcement agencies to descry, prognosticate and break crimes at a important faster rate and therefore reduces the crime rate. This can be used in other countries or countries depending upon the vacuity of the dataset.

I. INTRODUCTION

Felonious conditioning are present in every region of the world affecting quality of life and socio- provident development. As similar, it's a major concern of numerous governments who are using different advanced technology to attack similar issues. Crime Analysis, a sub branch of criminology, studies the behavioral pattern of felonious conditioning and tries to identify the pointers of similar events. Machine literacy agents work with data and employ different ways to find patterns in data making it veritably useful for prophetic analysis. Law enforcement agencies use different patrolling strategies grounded on the information they get to keep an area secure. A machine learning agent can learn and dissect the pattern of circumstance of a crime grounded on the reports of former felonious conditioning and can find hotspots grounded on time, type or any other factor. This fashion is known as bracket and it allows to prognosticate nominal class markers. Bracket has been used on numerous different disciplines similar as fiscal request, business intelligence, healthcare, rainfall soothsaying etc. In this exploration, a dataset from San- Francisco Open Data(8) is used which contains the reported felonious conditioning in the neighborhoods of the megacity San Francisco for a duration of 12 times. I used different bracket ways like Decision Tree, Naive Bayesian, Logistic Retrogression, k-Nearest Neighbor, Ensemble styles to find hotspots of felonious conditioning grounded on the time of day. Results of different algorithms have been compared and utmost the effective approach has also been proved.

II. EXISTING SYSTEM

- For the accessing of any information, one has to dig up piles of data manually.
- More time is needed in searching the required information.
- Bulks of hard copies are required to be referred.
- Access is not available anywhere.
- The increasing crime in our country is a big issue for us. To solve this issue, various systems are developed but they cannot find the area where the crime will happen.
- But it is not possible to keep all the records in memory or in file because of large data.

The large amount data maintenance is the big problem; searching and predicting a particular data manually is not possible from the files.2022 4th International Conference on Advances in Computing, Communication Control

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

In the proposed system,

- we are introducing the application which will predict the crime that criminals can do in the future.
- This prediction is based on attributes like criminal record, Criminal Damage, Weapons violation, Narcotics, Burglary, Theft and other offences and location like apartment, School, Public, Grounds, Streets, Residence, Parking lots etc.
- We will store all the previous record of criminal activities and we can calculate the possibility and prediction of the crime using Machine Learning Algorithms core as Python.
- K-Nearest Neighbor is one of the simplest Machine Learning algorithms based on Supervised Learning technique.

- Assumes the similarity between the new case/data and available cases and put the new case into the category that is most similar to the available categories.
- Stores all the available data and classifies a new data point based on the similarity. This means when new data appears then it can be easily classified into a well suite category by using KNN algorithm

IV. CONCLUSION

Throughout the research it has been evident that basic details of a criminal activities in an area contains indicators that can be used by machine learning agents to classify a criminal activity given a location and date. Even though the learning agent suffers from imbalanced categories of the dataset, it was able to overcome the difficulty by oversampling and undersampling the dataset. Through the experiments, it can be seen the imbalanced dataset was benefitted by using ENN undersampling. Using the undersampled data, Adaboost decision tree successfully classified criminal activities based on the time and location. With a accuracy of 81.93%, it was able to outperform other machine learning algorithms. Imbalanced classes are one of the main hurdles to achieve a better result. Though the machine learning agent was able to predictive model out of simply crime data, a demographic dataset would probably help to further improve the result and solidify it

V. OUTPUT

VI. REFERENCES

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